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Computers and Turbans: Exploring the Indian Middle Class through Pran's Comic World

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Abstract:

Pran Kumar Sharma created his characters for the Hindi monthlies *Lotpot* and *Madhu Muskaan* in the early Seventies, and all of them went on to harbour separate titles as standalone comic books from the mid Seventies. This paper aims to unearth the socio-political layers of Pran's world, pitted against the Goliath of globalisation, draw substantial parallels with the then-contemporary middle-cinema of Hrishikesh Mukherjee, Basu Chatterjee, and Sai Paranjpey, and affirm the battle between the Indian spirit of *aatma-shakti* and *chintan-manan* versus the looming danger of the very tangible yet enigmatic Western modernity.

Keywords: 'Bharatiya' Way, Middle class, Globalisation, Consumerism, Tension.

"We began in bluff. We continued in bluff. However, there was a notable difference. We began in innocence, believing in the virtue of the smell of sweat. We continued with knowledge of poverty and power." – V.S. Naipaul, *The Mimic Men* (1967)

The comic strip featuring Chacha Chaudhry first appeared in 1969 in the Hindi magazine *Lot Pot*. Gaining popularity in the early 1970s, Pran Kumar Sharma introduced characters such as Shreematiji, Raman, Billu, Pinky, and Channi Chachi, who also appeared in other Hindi

periodicals like *Madhu Muskan* and *Sarita*. A few years later, in 1976, Diamond Comics, an imprint of Diamond Pocket Books, launched a complete comic series starring these beloved characters. Sharma drew inspiration from Indian historical figures, especially Chanakya, renowned for his wisdom as the advisor to the ancient Emperor Chandragupta Maurya. Rather than following conventional Western comic hero archetypes, such as the physically powerful and handsome Superman, Sharma crafted a non-traditional hero. He envisioned an older man, slightly frail, unobtrusive, but possessing extraordinary intelligence. Chacha Chaudhry was characterised by his prominent bald head, often covered with a red turban, with a recurring joke humorously suggesting that the turban "protected" his brain from falling out. The turban's symbolism holds significance, representing the traditional Indian male and embodying wisdom and austerity. The bald head was a reminiscence of the historical figure of Chanakya. Interestingly, the title "Chacha" (meaning "Uncle" in Hindi) strongly resonated with Indian audiences, fostering emotional bonds between the character and the people. In modern Indian history, even Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru, the country's first Prime Minister, was affectionately called "Chacha Nehru," which may have subtly influenced the character's name. The word "Chacha" conveyed familial warmth in the Indian context, creating a deep emotional connection between the hero and the masses. This approach also drew from a traditional Indian narrative that often associates wisdom with senior figures. By making the hero an older man, Pran challenged the dominance of young, physically powerful American heroes from Marvel, DC, and King Features Syndicate. (The reader might also note that Professor Charles Xavier from Marvel's X-Men comics is a wheelchair-bound paraplegic who isn't traditionally heroic in appearance, but is one of the most intelligent minds around and, he too, is bald.)

Chacha Chaudhry was not just a *Chacha*—an affectionate Indian uncle—but also a *Chaudhry*, the respected figure of authority and recognition whom people turned to in times of

crisis He was the quintessential Indian patriarch, the upholder of values and social morality. The adage “*Computer se bhi tez dimag*” (a mind sharper than a computer) reflected the Indian middle class's scepticism toward the rapid influx of Western modernity and its perceived conflict with traditional Indian values.

Furthermore, the character of Sabu—Chacha’s brawny counterpart—was crafted in the model of the archetypal Western superhero. Much like DC’s Superman, who hails from Krypton, Sabu was portrayed as an alien from Jupiter, embodying similar superhuman traits. Nevertheless, he did not have the stylish cape or the spandex suit. He was nowhere near that aesthetic. Completing the subversion of the American superhero, Sabu wore a pair of drab Indian *chaddis* (shorts) and had round earrings adorning his ears. Moreover, he had a moustache and was bald. Consequently, he resembled the traditional Indian *pehlwan* from the *akhada*—a familiar figure popularised by *The Great Gama* and widely represented in popular culture by Dara Singh.

Shrimati Ji, the newly urbanised homemaker; Raman, the well-meaning local simpleton; Billu, the boy-next-door aspiring to be a cricketer (a sport gaining popularity in India during the late seventies); Channi Chachi, the gossiping neighbourhood ‘aunty’; and Pinky, the lonely young girl in semi-urban Delhi—all serve as symbols of the Indian middle class man’s last desperate attempt to assert the supremacy of the ‘Bharatiya way’ over the incoming American technocorporate culture that is soon to take over. The phrase ‘Bharatiya way’ warrants closer scrutiny, as it does not merely equate to tradition. The *antarjnaat* occurs when the values of the educated Indian middle class—its insecurities, everyday joys and frustrations, and conscious preference for the ordinary over the ostentatious—are fully recognised and understood. Traditionally, knowledge has been created, preserved, and maintained mainly within the framework of oral culture. Bhartrhari

asserts that knowledge originates from within our inner self. This knowledge is then shaped through the senses (*indriya*), which the mind (*man*) and intellect (*buddhi*) process. Eventually, this knowledge leads to a refined and aware self, known as the *chitta* (as described in *Vakyapadiya*, 1.112-14). Therefore, although perception and reasoning (inference) are central to Indian epistemology, argumentation (*tark*) also holds significant importance. However, Indian philosophy does not solely depend on sensory and cognitive faculties for acquiring knowledge; instead, it stresses the importance of meditation (*chintan*) and deep contemplation (*manan*) in forming knowledge. This knowledge considers elements of prioritising society over the self and includes an awareness of the self's origins when executing an action. Knowledge thus gained is in stark contrast with the Western school of rationality, which depends on material objectivity.

In *Chacha Chaudhry aur Aaj ka Robinhood*, Chaudhry tells Sabu to choose a new attire that would be more 'suitable' for his muscular, heroic physique (exuding virile masculinity), and Sabu returns, buying a coloured *chaddi* instead of a black one. The humour here is self-aware, yet it subtly carries the Indian notion of *paurush* (manhood) as something rooted in action rather than appearance. The reader must note the contrast in perception of masculinity. Post-2000s, virile masculinity is often associated with a display of sculpted muscles and choreographed dance moves, embodied by the urban, metro-sexual Bollywood hero. This idea extends to the trend of flaunting gym photos on Instagram. In stark contrast stands the raw, unpolished masculinity of Sabu—earthy, strong, and unconcerned with appearance. The focus in Pran's art, even when he drew Sabu's trunks and biceps in adequate detail, was never on making him desirable to the gendered senses. Despite being an overpowered alien, Sabu never found his way onto wall posters alongside figures like Sylvester Stallone or Arnold Schwarzenegger. This was not only because he was a *desi* character, but also due to his asexualised representation, which resisted any projection

of colonial desire. Sabu was not a caricature, but rather a mildly grotesque depiction of masculine strength—grotesque in the sense that, although the reader might not laugh at him, they would also never feel compelled to *mimic* him. Pran’s visual subversion of the emerging tropes of consumerism—especially in the wake of economic liberalisation in the early 1990s—became evident in his sketches of Sabu. His characters remained distinctly ‘Bharatiya’, rooted in a world that resisted the encroaching influence of the American corporate “Hybridity is the sign of the productivity of colonial power, its shifting forces and fixities; it is the name for the strategic reversal of the process of domination through disavowal (that is, the production of discriminatory identities that secure the ‘pure’ and original identity of authority)” says Homi K Bhabha in his seminal 1994 work, *The Location of Culture*. Pran’s world reveals curious forms of linguistic and ontological hybridity, where identities—though initially borrowed from the ‘desirable’ West—gradually subvert their Western origins. These transformed identities become something altogether different: not entirely Western, yet not wholly Indian either, thereby occupying a liminal, “third space”.

Chacha Chaudhry’s pet is a *desi* Indian mongrel, but is titled Rocket, making the tension between the Indian ethos and the gizmo-lure of the Western lexicon all the more palpable, and providing the dog an identity which limits him in a peculiar space of not being able to embrace his Indian mongrel self, and not willing to transform into a superior Western mould either. The word ‘rocket’ is culled out of the American realm of the unreachable, primarily championed by the glitz of technological supremacy and finesse. Pran takes this basic word and christens it unto a dog who is not a German shepherd or a Labrador, but a common Indian pariah. This nomenclature reflects the attitude of Chaudhry’s family in having a pet, not as a status symbol tied to owning an exotic breed, but as an expression of the inherent Indian *seva bhaav* (spirit of service), rejecting

superficial social climbing through material display. Furthermore, the name “Rocket” itself embodies the classic middle class spirit of resistance, as if declaring, “So what if he is an unimpressive mongrel? He is no less than your rockets.” One can almost hear Pran challenging the West, rejecting the idea that technological superiority alone grants a culture the right to assert dominance, especially through the seductive pathways of techno-corporate capitalism. He owns the mongrel because he loves him—there ends Chaudhry’s requirement. He has an outright alien living in his home, but he chooses to shelter a mongrel rather than purchasing a fancy breed. Once again, he names the mongrel “Rocket—not “Bhola” or “Chintu”—as a form of protest against the American giant flexing its financial muscle. It is a response to the West’s obsessive glorification of technology, aimed at dazzling the Third World into a cycle of consumption and endless consumerism. There is bitterness, cluelessness, and perhaps even some ignorance in Pran’s stance—but above all, there is an urgent desire to remind his readers to hold onto what makes them Indian: their *mulyabodh* (moral consciousness or value system).

Chacha Chaudhry also owns an ambiguously ‘alive’ truck named Dugdug. Not a car or a motorbike, but a truck—a heavy carriage vehicle that once again signifies Chacha Chaudhry’s identity as a North Indian man. He is not attached to luxurious ways of living, nor does he indulge in flaunting boastful swagger; rather, he is a symbol of honest hard work, which may be better understood as *parishram* and *purusharth*. In Chacha’s choice of vehicle, we catch a whiff of rebellion—or at least a hint of unease—with the shifting ideals of urban and semi-urban Indians, who seem to be ominously gravitating towards the seductive excesses of Western materialism.

This tension brings us to a comparison between R.K. Laxman’s iconic “common man” and Chacha Chaudhry. A close reading of the two offers valuable insights into the evolving

consciousness of the middle class in India. Laxman's 'common man', described as "no mere cartoon figure of fun, but the soul of modern India," serves as a passive observer of historical events and the effects of government policies on the middle class. He represents the ordinary citizen, witnessing the nation's turmoil in silence, embodying the frustrations of a people grappling with inefficient governance, corporate colonisation, and an overall decline in ethics. Laxman's portrayal suggests that the middle class is largely passive, enduring rather than acting. His 'common man' is, more often than not, a cynical observer, voiceless in the face of the erosion of 'Bharatiya' values, traded away for imported utilitarianism. Conversely, Chacha Chaudhry emerges as an active agent of social and political change. Unlike Laxman's 'Common man,' who is resigned to his fate, Chacha Chaudhry recognises systemic faults and takes steps to resolve them. He is not a mere bystander; he actively pursues justice, exposing wrongdoers and correcting socio-economic fallacies, often from a moral standpoint. While Laxman's 'Common man' represents a passive middle class disillusioned with the nation's moral decline, Chacha Chaudhry represents an assertive middle class that seeks to reform and transform society for the better. Chaudhry's character marks a notable departure from the cynicism that characterises Laxman's depiction of the middle class. Whereas the 'common man' passively accepts his fate, silently witnessing the failures of the state, Chaudhry embodies a more assertive figure—one who reclaims the middle class's role as a driving force in national development.

In this light, Pran's creation repositions the middle class as pivotal to the country's economic and social rejuvenation. An example of this is evident in the Chacha Chaudhry aur Tiranga, where Chacha Chaudhry, portrayed as a national figure, decides to retire from his self-appointed role of solving societal issues. The news of his retirement sends shockwaves across the country, encouraging anti-nationalists to capitalise on the situation by rallying American magnates

to exploit the nation. In response, the people beg Chaudhry to remain active to protect the nation from impending chaos. In a twist, Chacha reveals that his retirement was a mere ruse to catch the Americans off guard. Through this narrative, Chaudhry is portrayed as a steadfast leader whose wisdom is indispensable for safeguarding the nation's well-being. The middle class, represented by Pran's characters, thus emerges as the moral and cultural backbone of the nation. Overall, this comparison highlights a shift in the portrayal of the Indian middle class—from Laxman's passive, silent sufferer to Pran's empowered, problem-solving hero. No matter how childish or insignificant this act of rebellion might now seem, Pran's depiction of the inherent tussle between material American modernity and the essence of the 'Bharatiya' value system, throughout the 1970s and 1980s — just before liberalisation and its aftermath — seems almost prophetic.

G.N. Devy's 2017 book *The Crisis Within* is structured around four distinct yet interrelated themes: the idea of 'knowledge' in Indian tradition(s), the trajectory of 'memory', the patterns of social exclusion and their effects on knowledge construction, and the impact of language and technology on the forms of knowledge and its dissemination. Echoes of these themes can be traced in the print culture of the 1970s and 1980s, as well as in the readership that engaged with Pran's creations. Being lowly priced chapbooks, the comic-book medium itself did not allow readers to look beyond the apparent, and being often regarded with disdain, the 'knowledge' imparted through Pran's works never really attained the scholarly chambers of academic introspection. Over time, memory—crystallised through the repeated invocation of names like Chacha Chaudhry, Billu, and Raman—firmly established them as unmistakably middle-class Indian figures. Therefore, with the growing impact of American consumerism, the urbanised Indians of the 2000s gradually lost touch with Pran and his people. However, the comics themselves contained a

persistent dichotomy between Western wonder and the mundaneness of Indian lives—between dazzling modernity and the toil of everyday life.

Notably, the comic books published by Diamond Comics were originally written in Hindi and only later translated into English for wider circulation. This shift in language significantly alters the narrative dynamics and, in turn, reshapes the politics surrounding the characters. For instance, the axe-wielding villain Raka is described in Hindi as a *bhayanak raakshas* (terrifying demon), but in English, he is reduced to merely a “dacoit.” This translation strips away the mythical layers of his backstory, such as his transformation after drinking a potion brewed by a jungle hermit. Similarly, adjectives like *duraatma* (evil soul), *wehshi* (savage), and *bhakshak* (devourer) are flattened into “terrible,” “wild,” and “greedy,” thereby diminishing the deeper allegorical significance of Raka as an embodiment of the *arishadvarga* or *shad-ripu*—the six cardinal vices in ‘Bharatiya’ theology: *kaam* (lust), *krodh* (anger), *lobh* (greed), *mad* (pride), *moh* (attachment), and *matsarya* (envy). Much like Asterix and Obelix, Chacha Chaudhry and Sabu confront these forces, not only through physical battles with Raka but more fundamentally as a resistance to the rising tide of these vices within the middle class psyche, increasingly seduced by consumerism.

The tension between English and the authenticity of Pran’s characters—alongside his vision of ‘Bharatiyata’ resisting the allure of the West—resonates with themes explored in middle-of-the-road cinema, or “middle cinema,” which emerged in Bombay (now Mumbai) during the 1970s and 1980s. We are reminded of Pyaremohan Allahabadi from Hrishikesh Mukherjee’s *Chupke Chupke* (1975), who, albeit comically, expresses strong disdain for the use of English in Hindi conversations. Similarly, in *Gol Maal* (1979), the characters Ramprasad and Laxmanprasad

embody a sharp cultural contrast: Ramprasad, with his moustache and kurta, represents discipline and traditional ideals, while Laxmanprasad, clean-shaven and dressed in flashy attire, represents irreverence, slackness, and a break from convention. The impostor cook Raghu in *Bawarchi* (1972) tries to hold on to a middle class family falling apart in a house titled *Shanti Niwaas*, and the widower Kailashpati in *Kisi Se Na Kehna* (1983) is wary of marrying his son off to an urban, English-speaking girl lest she destroys him and the household. All of these instances are centred on the same idea of defiance towards the onslaught of impending globalisation, or Western globalisation, to be precise.

In Pran's world, the middle class has often been treated with empathy rather than celebration, especially in narratives that go beyond Chacha Chaudhry. For instance, Raman, the local do-gooder in a Delhi colony, embodies the archetype of the lovable loser. Far from being conventionally successful by contemporary standards, Raman remains essential to the smooth functioning of his community. In *Raman aur Lottery Ticket*, he labours through daily hardships in hopes of winning a lottery prize of two lakh rupees—just enough to buy a car and save his clothes from being splashed by monsoon potholes on Indian roads. Ironically, his winning ticket ends up soaked in the very puddle he hoped to escape. Yet, instead of despairing, Raman finds a moment of redemption: he notices a pair of frogs nearby and saves them from an approaching car, scaring them away. In doing so, he consoles himself for not being able to own a car. The moment is sarcastic and tender, strikingly reminiscent of an R.K. Narayan story in its understated emotional register.

Raman evokes the quiet struggles of characters like Amol Palekar's Arun in *Chhoti Si Baat* (1975) and Naseeruddin Shah's Rajaram in *Katha* (1982)—middle class introverts earnestly trying

to live up to Western ideals of ‘suave smartness’ to win the affection of their respective love interests. Similarly, Raman finds it nearly impossible to get noticed by Shalini, the neighbourhood English teacher. He seeks advice from Channi Chachi, the rotund, gossipy aunt who frequently crosses over into his stories. Though loud and cantankerous, Channi Chachi occasionally offers unexpected wisdom, further enriching Pran’s cast of delightfully flawed yet relatable middle class figures.

Channi Chachi, Shreematiji, and Pinky were the three prominent female protagonists created by Pran, each representing the socio-political tensions faced by Indian middle class women. Though they belong to different age groups, all three navigate the dilemma of staying true to their indigenous identities or succumbing to the pull of becoming a *mimic* (wo)man, caught between tradition and Western influence.

Shreematiji, or Sheela (her given name), is a BA-qualified homemaker in her thirties. She is depicted as someone caught between modest domestic ambitions and the constraints of her husband’s insufficient salary. Her innocent desires—for a new mixer, a toaster, or even a tin of cosmetic snow—highlight the quiet struggles of the middle class. In *Shreematiji aur Sale*, she secretly takes her husband’s wallet to buy *sarees* on discount, only to lose it. Later, she learns the wallet contained air tickets to America, which her husband won in an office contest. In *Shreematiji aur Jamaalgota*, she sets out to buy laxatives for her husband. However, she impulsively stops for pizza on the way home—a food still symbolically foreign and culturally loaded at that time. Ironically, she ends up taking the laxatives herself because of the resulting indigestion. These humorous mishaps highlight her vulnerability within a consumer culture she neither fully resists nor completely understands.

Channi Chachi, by contrast, is a loud, gossipy woman in her mid-fifties—a typical character in an Indian middle class neighbourhood. Her meddlesome nature often leads to comic chaos. In *Channi Chachi ke Teen Bandar*, she takes her three mischievous nephews to a *katha pandal* to listen to religious sermons, hoping to reform their behaviour. Yet, once there, she starts gossiping about her neighbour Lallan's alleged affair with his office secretary, effectively hijacking the sermon and diverting the audience's attention from the speaker. Her behaviour, while absurd, reflects the noisy, contradictory moral landscape of everyday life in urban India. These stories make it clear that Pran did not portray his female protagonists as heroic opposers of consumerism. Instead, he depicted them as ordinary middle class individuals caught in the chaos of conflicting cultural forces. His characters are not paragons of virtue or rebellion, but hapless agents navigating the absurdity of their social realities.

Although Pran often mocks their follies and inconsistencies, he also humanises them. A poignant example appears in *Shreematiji ki Honeymoon*, where, after a series of comedic squabbles and misunderstandings, Shreematiji ultimately agrees—without resentment—to stay in a cramped house simply because she loves her husband. This moment reminds us of Basu Chatterjee's *Piya Ka Ghar* (1972), reassuring us of Pran's commitment to a value system rooted not in Western individualism but in emotional resilience, compromise, and relational ethics central to 'Bharatiyata'.

Pinky and Billu are two of the younger protagonists created by Pran, each capturing a unique slice of the Indian middle class experience. Pinky is a sweetly precocious five-year-old girl, often depicted as lonely and emotionally mature beyond her years; on the other hand, Billu is a cricket-loving fifteen-year-old perpetually looking for ways to escape his homework.

Pinky was loosely inspired by Ernie Bushmiller's comic-strip character *Nancy* (1922), but Pran firmly rooted her in the context of a late-1970s urban Indian middle class household. In *Pinky Aur Jaadugar*, she runs away from home after feeling neglected by her working parents. On a local train, she befriends a wandering magician—a plot reminiscent of Gulzar's *Kitaab* (1977). The magician, serving as a kind of moral anchor, brings her back home and gives her parents a 'magical' pendulum, telling them it would always sway in the direction of their daughter and remind them to return to her whenever they are too consumed by work. This tale, gently melancholic and whimsical, reflects the emotional alienation often faced by children of dual-income families in post-emergency urban India.

Billu, by contrast, embodies the rebellious, cricket-obsessed teenager of the 1980s. Constantly at odds with his neighbour Bajrangi Pehlwan—whose window panes he frequently shatters—Billu is Pran's way of illustrating youthful defiance. His obsession with cricket also mirrors a broader cultural shift. By the 1980s, especially after India's 1983 World Cup win, cricket had shed its colonial and elitist image, gaining mass popularity, slowly displacing football, which had been the more plebeian and thus accessible sport until the early 1970s.

Pran often used cricket as a metaphor to capture the tensions between the emerging middle class and the affluent elite. In *Billu ka Toss*, Billu exacts subtle revenge for his father's workplace humiliation by thrashing the boss's English-speaking, chewing-gum-spitting son—an arrogant fast bowler with flashy branded shoes—in a match. Billu hits three consecutive sixes with a humble local bat, impressing even the boy's NRI girlfriend. But just as the moment threatens to turn into a triumphant class victory, *mulyabodh* (moral consciousness) intervenes. In the final panels, Billu quietly walks away from the stadium before the prize distribution, letting his opponent save face.

The act of restraint affirms Pran's recurring belief in humility and ethical self-restraint over unchecked glory.

Lastly, mention must be made of Pran's anthropomorphic animal characters—Cheeku the hare, Bhondu the elephant, and Pintu the dog—who featured in *Maharaja Circus*. These characters appeared in standalone four-page stories alongside Chacha Chaudhry or Billu in the digest comic books, and occasionally in ensemble narratives. In one such comic strip titled “Karmabhoomi”, the trio unites to resist a pot-bellied white American tycoon intent on seizing the circus grounds to construct a plush shopping complex. Cheeku, Bhondu, and Pintu fight back with determination, eventually thwarting the sale and saving their beloved circus. Here, the circus—an emblem of nostalgia and old-school entertainment—emerges as a symbolic space under siege, representing the values of ‘Bharatiyata’ (Indianness) threatened by the onslaught of Western capitalism and modern consumerist culture. Pintu's declaration that the circus is their *karmabhoomi* (their field of duty) evokes a deep ethical and emotional commitment to resisting change for the sake of change. It affirms Pran's consistent message: that loyalty, belonging, and cultural rootedness matter more than the glamour of profit or progress.

The conflict between the humble circus and the glamorous business venture directly recalls Kundan Shah's *Doordarshan* series *Circus* (1988), where the septuagenarian Bau-ji and his US returned son Shekharan clash over whether to sell off the circus or preserve what appears to be an outdated mode of entertainment. In a similar vein, Pintu and his friends defend Maharaja Circus—not for its commercial viability, but for the emotional and ethical bond they share with it. Its owner, Bhashambhar Prasad, had raised them since they were pups and cubs, and their loyalty to him is unwavering. They insist that no amount of money could shake their love or gratitude toward the

circus and the man they consider both foster father and employer. Their actions echo the spirit of the Sanskrit shloka, “*Kṛtajña tātrayāḥ lokeṣu na prakāśayate yadā*,” which means, “Gratitude is not expressed in mere words until it is demonstrated.”

Pran and his depiction of middle class maladies resemble the final knockout punch of a weary boxer—delivered in a flash of brilliance just as he collapses into unconsciousness. This ‘punch’ may be read through the lens of Bhalchandra Nemade’s concept of “Nativism”. Colonialism and colonial culture historically positioned Indian traditions as a “low-value culture.” Nemade, in the 1980s, rightly emphasised the need to return to one’s *mool* (roots) and introduced “Desivad”, or “Nativism”, as a philosophical and behavioural framework to re-conceptualise, revisit, and reclaim one’s native identity. “Nativism”, in this sense, becomes a form of resistance—against the neo-colonial and neo-imperial forces of consumerist capitalism, and against the cultural hegemony imposed by Globalisation. It emerges as a vital weapon for cultures that are endangered, marginalised, or rendered hegemonic.

In the Indian pop-cultural context, “Nativism” offers an alternative model of national prosperity—one that seeks to preserve the *aatman* of the civilisation through an approach that is neither colonial nor globalised. India saw its native superhero in the form of Shaktimaan in the television series *Shaktimaan* as late as 1997—a time when there was no clear enemy left to fight, no war to wage. Globalisation had already occurred, and the essence of the West had firmly seeped into the Indian psyche. Yet, even at that terminal point, the mutiny endured, echoing the same spirit of resistance, most poignantly captured in the title song of the series, which proclaimed:

*“Yeh aatm-shakti hai, duniya badal sakti hai. Phoolon mein dhal sakti hai, sholon si jalsakti hai.
Hota hai jab aadmi ko, apna gyan, kehlaya woh Shaktimaan.”*

(The strength of the *aatman* renders it the tenderness of a flower, along with the raging heat of an ember. When a man knows his inner self to the core, he becomes *Shaktimaan*.) Pran and his un-heroic protagonists espoused a similar philosophy, infused with humour, and at times, tinged with pathos. They were two decades ahead of their time.

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